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MOTIVATING SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY STUDENTS TO USE SOCIAL THEORIES IN DESIGN PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

Students in a masters' programme for STEM teachers and Science Communication specialists at Delft University of Technology (DUT) participate in a design course, as designing course materials and communication products is part of their professional lives. Design in a non-technology context seems not to particularly motivate these students.

This research project investigated how monitoring students can be put to use in optimizing instructional strategies and course content. An optimized curriculum, it is reasoned, leads to better motivated students, better learning and better student products.

The expectancy-value theory and self-determination theory were used as a framework to measure motivation. A didactical approach with variations in instructional strategies contributed to highly motivated students.

Keywords: student motivation; design education; social design theories

INTRODUCTION

Students in the masters' programme for Science Education & Communication (SEC, Delft University of Technology) take a course in designing communication and education processes and products (DCEP), because, according to the programme's attainment targets, they have to be able to design processes and products in their professional lives. The course was first offered in 2007 and has been in the programme ever since. Participants have various backgrounds in science and technology on a bachelor level. Students prepare

themselves either for a teaching career or a career as science communication professional.

The course objectives are threefold: knowledge acquisition, especially of theories and models related to instructional and communication design (Van Merriënboer & Kirschner, 2007; Wehrmann & Van der Sanden, 2007), applying design knowledge and skills in a "guided practice environment" and self-regulated design of a realistic communication or education process and products. Processes and products should illustrate adequate and creative application of theories and models.

PROBLEM

Evaluation of previous years' courses indicated two problems. Students were not (intrinsically) motivated to explore and use the added value of social theories for design. This might be related to their background in science and technology: social theories might not automatically appeal to them. Education students seemed even less motivated than communication students: this might have to do with their focus on their future professional lives as secondary school teachers and their expectations about the course. Secondly, final student products seemed to lack sufficient application of design related theories.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In the academic year 2010-2011 the course was redesigned to counter the problems above, a new didactical approach was introduced. Objectives of this research project are to investigate whether this didactical approach motivates the students and enables them to reach the course objectives. The expectancy-value theory of

achievement motivation (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000) was used to operationalize motivation.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main question of our research is: How can students be motivated to apply social theories in designing education and communication products and processes.

We will find an answer to the main question by means of two sub-questions:

1. To what extent can students' motivation be positively influenced by instructional strategies and course content?
2. To what extent does high student motivation contribute to final student products in which relevant theoretical considerations contributed to quality of the products?

BACKGROUND

In this paragraph background information will be provided on motivation and the role of social theories in DCEP.

MASTER STUDENTS' MOTIVATION

The learning process within the DCEP-course could be characterized as self-regulated learning: students being responsible for their learning and design process.

Barak (2010) proposes a model for self-regulated learning (SRL) in a technology education context. The model consists of three elements: cognition, metacognition and motivation. Technology education and education about designing education and communication products and processes have a lot in common. We therefore assume that Barak's model and its constituent parts apply to students' learning behavior in the DCEP course.

Students need to have knowledge (*cognition*) about design methodologies and social theories in order to draw up solutions for the problem in the course's cases. It is interesting to note that Barak (2010) includes creativity and creative thinking in his view on cognition.

Students need *metacognitive skills* such as planning, monitoring progress and evaluation to structure their work individually as well as in groups. Reflective practice is a natural part of metacognition.

Obviously, *motivation* plays a major role in learning and performing well. On motivation Barak (2010, p. 386) refers to Hill (2007) identifying "... key factors affecting students' motivation to learn, for example, contextualization learning in the students' world, bringing real-world subjects into the classroom, giving the students choice, autonomy and control over their learning, and providing feedback."

A motivation theory which is often used in education is the expectancy-value theory of achievement motivation (Wigfield and Eccles, 2000). The authors offer a rather complex model of achievement motivation. To assess children's achievement motivation Wigfield and Eccles focus on three categories: *ability beliefs* (which focus on present abilities), *expectancy* (focus on future abilities) and *achievement values*: usefulness of the task (utility value), importance of doing well on the task (attainment value), interest / enjoyment gained from doing the task (intrinsic value). These concepts, and questionnaire items derived from them, seem to be adequate indicators of motivation in an education context.

We believe the concepts not only to apply to children, but to adult learners as well. Maybe they are even more prominent as adult learners are more used to reflect on their abilities, their expectancies and the value they attach to achieving learning tasks (Merriam et al, 2008).

A recent article by Berger and Karabenick (2011) explores the relationship between expectancy value theory and learning strategies, like self-regulated learning. They assessed motivation by an instrument, based on the Motivated Strategy for Learning Questionnaire (Pintrich, 1989). It includes 4 indicators of achievement *values*: utility, attainment value, interests and costs. Costs refer to how the decision to engage in one activity limits access to other activities. Self-efficacy was used as indicator of *expectancy*.

Berger and Karabenick (2011) concluded that motivation showed to be an adequate predictor of learning styles. Even though in our study we do not focus on learning styles, we used these variables to measure motivation.

Another theory on motivation relevant to the current context is developed by Ryan and Deci (2000). Their main concepts are extrinsic and intrinsic motivation and self-determination. In their theory of self-determination, a distinction is made between three fundamental needs, the fulfillment of which might explain the variability in intrinsic motivation: competence autonomy and relatedness. These needs are defined as:

- Competence: understanding how to solve a problem or complete an assignment and being self-efficacious in performing the necessary and sufficient actions;
- Autonomy: feeling free to initiate and regulate their own actions;
- Relatedness: ability to establish satisfying connections with members of the group.

In our study we asked students to assess these three needs.

SOCIAL THEORIES IN THE DCEP-COURSE

To teach students about design in education and communication we use different perspectives. Insights from education, communication and industrial design methodologies (Merriënboer & Kirschner, 2007; Schellens & Klaassen, 2002; Roozenburg & Eekels, 1998) and more general ideas about engineering in which technology and values are concerned (De Vries, 2005; Auyang, 2004) are the pillars of the DCEP-course.

On top of this, students are challenged to explore the utility of social theories not directly related to the design process, like motivation theories, personality theories, systems theory and evaluation theories. Our purpose is to broaden their scope and to justify their decisions in the designing process. We teach our students to consider designing social processes and products as an iterative process.

Figure 1 offers a schematic view of the design process introduced to the students in the DCEP course. A first stage is to *diverge* from the problem by thinking of all possible aspects related to content, context, target audience, etc. Students should experience that social theories, intuition and creativity play a major role in this stage.

To get a grip on this complexity a second, *converging* stage is introduced. Students construct their own theoretical framework. This framework is a collection and combination of selected social theories and concepts that can be put into use by the designer to focus and to support him in taking explicit decisions in the designing process.

The iterative character of the design process follows from repeating the diverging and converging stages several times. Every transition will be enriched by taking another perspectives or introducing other theoretical considerations. Social reality is never completely understandable from a theoretical point of view. Students will have to make use of intuition and creativity to optimize their theoretical framework.

Figure 1: Process of diverging and converging

DIDACTICAL APPROACH

The didactical approach is in line with the key factors influencing motivation mentioned by Hill (2007): using real-world problems, giving students

control and autonomy and provide them with feedback.

The DCEP-course is built on three principles: 1) *content*: lectures on design theories, social theories and related subjects, 2) *practice*: guided practice in solving a commonly recognizable problem with characteristics of both education and communication and 3) *reflection* on theory and guided practice.

The DCEP-course consists of two parts.

The *first* part covers knowledge acquisition and a guided practice. Our objective was to prepare students to integrate theory and practice. Students attend lectures covering various subjects such as design methodology, dual nature of technological artefacts, systems theory, motivation theories (expectancy-value theory and self-determination theory were included in this part of the course) and evaluation methods. Immediately following the lectures, students progressed in study groups through a step by step, guided, design process. This year's case focussed on designing communication and education based solutions for the unacceptably high percentage of DUT's bachelor students who fail to successfully conclude their studies in the nominal three years and the equally unacceptable high attrition rates. Students recognised the importance of the case as it was very close to their own more or less recent experiences.

Although in this process guidance was offered, we tend to label it as (modest form of) self-regulated learning, students being responsible for their learning and design process.

The *second* half of the course is mainly dedicated to a self-regulated realistic design. In accordance with their future careers in education or science communication students design a series of course modules on nanotechnology and mathematical modelling or a communication strategy and plan to promote the introduction of "SmartCard", an innovative product from a Dutch firm. In contrast to the first part lecturers provided no additional theoretical content.

METHOD

INTERVENTIONS AND INSTRUMENTS

To answer the research questions a mixed methods design was used. At the beginning of the course the students' expectations and their experiences with designing were assessed (t=0 survey).

Each meeting started off with an 'inspirational session': the lecturer asked students to report on an inspiring and course related subject which hit the news in previous days. This elicited lively discussions among the students.

All seven four-hours course meetings were split in two. The first two hours were devoted to a lecture on an academic subject. During the 3rd and 4th hours students worked in subgroups on their assignments, applying the lecture's content. To monitor students' knowledge acquisition, motivation and attitudes they filled in questionnaires, half-way and at the end of each meeting.

The half-way questionnaire focussed on students' perception of what was learned and whether they felt inspired by the lecture they attended. Furthermore they were asked to name the instructional strategies the lecturer had used and their evaluation thereof. We call this the monitoring survey (mon 1)

At the end of each meeting (mon 2) students were asked to indicate their perception of what was learned and whether they felt inspired by the group session they took part in. Again their evaluation of instructional strategies was assessed. Finally students were asked which questions they would like to have answered in the next lecture.

Questionnaires were instantly analyzed by the lecturers and researchers. Analysis led to decisions whether or not to adapt the instructional strategies or course content.

After the fourth meeting, when expectancy-value and self-determination theories of motivation were explained, students were asked to evaluate whether their motivation varied depending on different instructional strategies (EVT/SDT-survey)

The following instructional strategies were included:

- Traditional lecture
- Interactive lecture
- Reflection
- Working in group
- Working for the group (e.g. from home)
- Reading and preparing for lectures

Indicators for motivation were inspired by Berger and Karabenick (2011) and by Ryan and Deci (2000):

EVT - Value

- Interest
- Utility
- Attainment Value (Importance)
- Cost

EVT - Expectancy

- Self-efficacy

SDT

- Competence
- Autonomy
- Relatedness

Instructors closely followed the achievements of the student groups. Homework was evaluated and commented and feedback was provided in the groups. Feedback was positively worded and focused at the direction of solutions proposed by groups, their use of social theories and concepts. If applicable suggestions were made to adhere to the diverging / converging process.

When students reported dissatisfaction with the instructional strategies, adjustments were made in subsequent lectures. Depending on the relevance of questions that students liked to be answered lecture content was adapted. If a question was relevant for only one or two groups, lectures remained unchanged; answers to these questions, however, were included in the feedback to the group.

Throughout the course lecturers had frequent informal contacts with students in order to observe satisfaction or dissatisfaction or possible flaws in motivation. Notes were taken from these contacts.

The quality of the students' products, was assessed by the lecturers. Main criteria were: link between theory and practice, and sufficient application of design related theories.

Part of the final assignment (a design report including a theoretical framework) every student also wrote an individual portfolio. In this portfolio they reflected on what they had learned.

Questionnaires and interviews with students were used to verify whether the interventions led to the intended motivational effects.

In the second part of the course, students' design processes were closely monitored through observation and interviews and students' logs. The main focus was on the link between theory and practice. The final products were assessed by independent assessors.

SUBJECTS

In the 2010-2011 course 25 students participated (13 education students and 12 communication students). The youngest student was 22, the eldest 59, the average age was 27.

There were three international students, therefore the course was taught in English. In subgroups, however, students often reverted to Dutch. Seven students combined their masters' programme with a (part time) job as secondary education teacher.

Students had various backgrounds as indicated by their preceding bachelor programmes in for example chemistry, aerospace engineering, applied physics, industrial design, applied mathematics. Eight students already had a masters' degree; the MSc in Science Education and Communication would be their second.

Although not explicitly assessed, we feel students varied in their ability to cope with uncertainty. Especially some of the younger students with a physics or mathematics background seemed unfamiliar with assignments "where no right answer exists for". Elder students and students with a background in industrial design did not show this kind of fear for uncertainty.

Students with a background in science seem to have problems coping with uncertainties and lack of 'how to' prescriptions in particular.

RESULTS

EXPECTATIONS

From the t=0 survey at the beginning of the course, students were highly motivated. They expected to gain knowledge and skills relevant for their professional career.

Marc (Math Education): *"I need it for my work as a teacher"*. Miranda (Science Communication and Industrial Design): *"As a communication professional you have to design and develop communication products"*.

Moreover, from both the t=0 survey and evaluations of former courses we know that the science education students expect to learn about how to design a proper series of lessons and the according material. Peter (Computer Science Education): *"I want to make my own course materials suitable for a specific target group, taking the learning goals into account. Besides that I would like to make attractive material that motivates my students."*

Whereas the science communication students have a less clear and well defined expectation of the course. Robert (Science Education and Aerospace Engineering): *"Learn to understand communication principles via physical products and apply the theory."*

STUDENT CHARACTERISTICS AND MOTIVATION

Based on experiences in former years, we supposed that the focus of the education students on professional practice leads to a decrease of motivation to learn about theory. Results from the EVT/SDT-survey show that the motivation for both groups E and C are quite similar. Some minor differences in motivation seem to appear when students with a Bachelor degree in Industrial Design and Applied Physics are compared. Therefore it is more likely that differences in motivation are related to differences in Bsc-backgrounds of the students.

USE OF THEORY

The monitoring surveys showed that most students had difficulties in getting grip on the complexity of the case and in using theory in the design process. At the start of the course they did not feel confident about the diverging and converging process of ideas

and solutions. Michel (Computer Science Education): *"First you have to broaden your vision, than narrow it down, than broaden it again with help of motivation theory. Why?"*

The students with a science background felt at the beginning of the course overwhelmed by theory, whereas the design students thought that their creativity was not of any use anymore. Anne: *"I miss the creative incentive. By sticking to theories, it seems your freedom is limited."*

The construction of a theoretical framework did not take away these feelings of discomfort at first. Students familiar with design stuck to their intuition and belief in creativity. Peter: *"In spite of (or thanks to) theory, there is still a lot of creativity in the design process"*. Marc: *"The Industrial Designer wants to propose as much ideas as possible and doesn't want to make choices. The physicist wants explicit choices."*

Students with a science background proved to have a quite rigid idea about theories and their practical use. Eddy (Math Education): *"Mathematical theories are very different from the theories we use here."*

Students asked for structure during the courses and in the evaluations. Anne (Science Communication and Industrial Design): *"As long as I don't see the goal or especially the usefulness of an activity, I cannot focus on the task or subject."*

Most students saw theories as prescribing reality, although we tried to teach them that theories can be used to understand and analyze reality as well. A combination of theories in a framework could provide them with a more sophisticated instrument to analyze reality. It took students about three lectures and three study groups to gain these insights. Karen (Science Communication and Chemical Engineering): *"The process to solve the problem was consistent: the theories, concepts and models that come across. In other words: you get a better insight and more grip."* Michel: *"It took some time, and the theory and methods remained vague, but now I get it, now we're getting more concrete."*

STUDY GROUPS

Study groups, as we learned from results of the monitoring surveys and what we observed in class, were of importance to share ideas and feelings on

Figure 2: Expectancy value theory: Average group score per instructional strategy.

TL=Traditional Lecture; IL=Interactive Lecture; REF=Reflection; WinG=Work in Group; WwithG= Work with Group; Prep=Preparation

Figure 3: Self-determination theory: Average group score per instructional strategy

TL=Traditional Lecture; IL=Interactive Lecture; REF=Reflection; WinG=Work in Group; WwithG= Work with Group; Prep=Preparation

the utility of theories. Richard (Science Communication and Chemistry): *"The discussion on the theories helped me think about the project."* Janneke: *"It is a nice feeling if the theories fit to each other en match with our project."*

As can be seen in figure 2 (EVT) and figure 3 (SDT) both working in study groups and interactive lectures were valued highly. The study groups and interactive lectures supported the students: these didactic methods got high scores on interest, self-efficacy, competence, autonomy and relatedness. Traditional learning motivated students less. Students accept

classical lectures to a certain extent. Eddy: *"It is suitable, it is a good way to give information."*

THEORY, CREATIVITY & STRUCTURE

During the course students became more and more familiar with the idea that theory and creativity are complementary instead of contradicting one another.

They realized that academic reasoning and design is all about structuring your creative and theoretical reasoning. Steven (Science Communication and Mechanical Engineering): *"The theoretical framework becomes some kind of check and not a route map, while I thought that was the very essence of such a framework."*

Students were very well able to use theories in their reports. Various social theories and motivation theories were included in the theoretical framework. Students succeeded in creatively using different theories. One of the student groups, for example, developed a matrix combining various stages of the organizational process (i.e. the process of making contact with prospective students, establishing a relationship with them and monitoring their first year's courses as DUT students) with communication and education theories and instruments derived from theories. The matrix increased their insight and made tangible how organizational stages in time could be supported dynamically by communication and education theories and instruments.

Overall, the results suggest that through monitoring valid information on student motivation can be obtained. Moreover, the results validate the EVT and SDT theory. On course level we see that theory, creativity and structure by making use of interactive lectures and study groups lead to higher student motivation.

CONCLUSIONS

The problems raised in former courses turned out to be solved in this year's DCEP-course: both education and communication students were motivated and they showed to be able of implementing social design theories into their education and science communication products.

The didactical approach of providing students with knowledge about design theories and social theories, teaching them metacognitive skills to structure their work individually as well as in groups and providing them with feedback in order to deal with uncertainty proved to be a good means to motivate students.

Although the overall motivation of students was high, there was no sign of a specific motivation variable being significantly different from others: none of the variables derived from the expectancy-value theory (utility, attainment, interest, and costs) nor those from the self-determination theory (competence, autonomy and relatedness). Motivation as measured seemed to be a coherent concept.

When we have a look at the instructional strategies, working in (small) groups turned out to contribute most to students' motivation.

DISCUSSION

The results found in this research project seem to indicate that the didactical approach based on the key factors mentioned by Hill (2007), indeed lead to motivated and well-performing students.

However, the number of students in our study was relatively small: the results are not conclusive and should be interpreted as a possible trend. The lecturers' engagement to this design of communication and education processes and products course may have had a positive influence on student motivation as well.

The study was focused on the first part of the DCEP course. Whether the motivational effects will last into the second part as well, could not yet be

established. Evaluation of products and students' motivation in the second part of the course will generate a more profound answer to research question two.

Further research could verify whether motivation effects could be obtained in other educational situations with a comparable didactical approach.

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